

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable D2.1

A framework to assess soil threats, soil functions and soil-based ecosystem services

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of Task 2.1, WP2 within the SERENA project was to ‘Report about the concepts used in SERENA (soil quality, soil health, soil threats, soil functions, soil-based ES, bundles) with their associated definitions, and develop a framework linking these concepts’. A list of fifteen soil related terms that are key within the SERENA project was drawn up. From several different data sources being past EU projects, scientific institutes and literature, definitions for these terms were gathered and evaluated in a task group formed by several SERENA partners. After this, the most appropriate definitions were selected and sometimes adapted. This draft list was then evaluated by all SERENA partner institutes and using their comments, the task group drew up the final definitions list.

Several alternative conceptual frameworks were developed for SERENA based on the definitions of key terms and the SIREN conceptual framework as the basis. After evaluating these alternatives, a draft conceptual framework was developed that is presented in this report. The draft framework, and the definitions when needed, will be evaluated during the course of the project and be adapted if necessary.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
CF	Conceptual Framework
ES	Ecosystem Services
SES	Soil Ecosystem Services
Tx.y	Task x.y
OBx.y	Objective x.y
Mx.y	Milestone x.y

1. Introduction

Definitions form an important part of the work in a scientific research project; they form the cornerstones upon which the rest of the work is built. Without explicit agreement about the meaning of specific (scientific) terms and concepts, it becomes very difficult to execute the rest of the research in a project, since misunderstanding and confusion can form a serious obstruction. In the SERENA project, WP2 deals with ‘Definitions, conceptual Framework, and harmonized methodologies’, and forms an important basis for the rest of the work in the project. Task 2.1 is in charge of compiling a list of the most important definitions that will be used in the course of the project. The output of Task 2.1 is based on the objectives OB2.1 and OB2.2.

2. Objectives and output of T2.1

2.1. Objectives

The objectives of T2.1 were described in the SERENA proposal:

“OB2.1: to define soil threats, soil-based ecosystem services, and the concept of bundles, in accordance with the other concepts describing the overall status of the soil system.

We will compare definitions and indicators describing soil threats and ecosystem services in accordance with end-users / stakeholders’ inputs (task 1.2) to define bundles.

Special attention will be paid to human health issues as regards the Soil Mission Board and soil quality and soil health definitions. The way threshold and reference values are defined and used to interpret indicators will also be studied (e.g., using the outputs of previous research projects as SIREN)”.

“OB2.2: to provide a synthetic conceptual framework describing the links between soil threats and soil-based ES, using the intermediate concept of soil functions.

Soil Quality and Soil Health indicators are commonly used to calculate indicators of soil threats and/or soil-based ES. Based on the concepts defined in OB2.1, this objective is dedicated to build a comprehensive framework to link all the concepts, in order to facilitate the implementation of indicators, and the interpretation of data and maps produced in WP3 and WP5”.

2.2. Output

Task 2.1 has two specific outputs according to the SERENA proposal:

- **Milestone M2.1** (Definitions of soil threats, soil-based ES, soil quality, soil health (based on literature review and analysis of previous EU projects about soil threats and soil-based ES), and
- **Deliverable D2.1** (Report about the concepts used in SERENA (soil quality, soil health, soil threats, soil functions, soil-based ES, bundles) with their associated definitions, and a framework linking these concepts).

The delivery date for Milestone M2.1 is month 6 (end of April 2022), while the delivery date for Deliverable D2.1 is month 8 (end of June 2022). This report is Deliverable D2.1.

3. General selection procedure for soil related terms and definitions to be used in SERENA

The approach in this task consisted of the following steps:

- a. Selection of task-team members
- b. Selection of soil related terms to develop definitions for
- c. Selection of data sources
- d. First selection of definitions and in-team discussions
- e. SERENA -wide discussion and commenting
- f. Proposed final selection

3.1.Task 2.1 Definitions task group members

The following group of people volunteered to work on soil-, soil threat- and soil ecosystem services - related definitions: **the definitions task group**.

Name	Role	Institute	Beneficiary (B) / Linked party (L)
Lennart Fuchs	Group member	WR, Netherlands	B2
Kees Teuling	Group member	WR, Netherlands	B2
Erik van den Elsen	Task leader	WR, Netherlands	B2
Agnieszka Klimkowicz-Pawlas	Group member	IUNG, Poland	B18
Jacek Niedźwiecki	Task co-leader	IUNG, Poland	B18
David Montagne	Group member	APT, France	L1
Ottone Scammacca	Group member	APT, France	L1
Thomas Weninger	Group member	BAW, Austria	L7

3.2.Selection of definitions: the process explained

The task leader of the group proposed the following workflow for selecting the definitions, which was agreed upon by the definitions task group:

Step 1	Jointly draw up a list of terms
Step 2	Create a set of possible candidates for definitions from various data sources
Step 3	Selection process within the task group
Step 4	Draft list of definitions
Step 5	Selection process by the SERENA project partners
Step 6	Final list of definitions

3.3. Step 1 - Relevant soil related terms, definitions and data sources

As was mentioned in the introduction, definitions form the cornerstones upon which the rest of the work in the project is built. It is vital that there is agreement and unambiguity regarding terms that are

being used in the project. First a list of relevant terms was created by taking the terms that were already defined in the T2.1 task text. This list was expanded with terms that the task group thought to be relevant for the project. This base list of terms was called the ‘blue list’ for easy reference and is given in Table 1.

A broad inventory of definitions from various data sources was already proposed in the project proposal. During the work we found some other relevant data sources. The list of data sources below was used to make a broad overview of definitions for the terms in the blue list. Behind the different data sources are the partner organizations within the task team (in red) who took care of the specific part of the inventory.

1. EU projects ISQAPER, RECARE, LANDMARK -> WR
2. EJP SOIL Glossary -> WR
3. Other EJP projects (SIREN, MINOTAUR) – linked to SIREN: EEA report (Soil Indicator Thresholds, Baritz et al. 2022 – in prep.) -> WR
4. Experience from member states (SERENA colleagues?) -> Later
5. Soil Mission Board and ITPS (soil health) -> APT
6. Definition of the BUNDLES concept -> BAW
7. Scientific Literature -> IUNG

Table 1 The ‘blue list’; the list of selected definition terms.

1	Soil quality	9	Ecosystem service / soil threat bundle
2	Soil health	10	Service providing unit
3	Soil fertility	11	Service providing area
4	Soil function	12	Soil degradation
5	Soil threat	13	Thresholds
6	Ecosystem services	14	Reference values
7	Soil Ecosystem Services	15	Target value
8	Indicator		

The definitions found throughout the various data sources were then placed in a single Excel sheet, together with the source (an impression of the Excel sheet: Figure 1), see Annex 1 for the complete sheet reference.

The definitions used in the EJP soil glossary and especially the SIREN project (Faber et al., 2022) received our special attention, since these definitions have been developed quite recently, with the latest state-of-the-art knowledge in science (and might therefore be more up to date), and within the context of the EJP soil project and European policies on agriculture and climate.

3.4. Step 2 & 3 - Definition terms and first selection of definitions

The first selection of most relevant definitions was made by members of the task group by voting by organization in the task group on the most preferred definition. The remaining definition was discussed and adapted when found necessary.

Selection of the definitions was done by voting for every separate term using a ‘traffic light’ system: green = preferred, orange = possible, red = not suitable. The result of this vote can be seen in Figure 1. This Excel sheet then formed the basis for discussions and was finalized by the draft list of definitions (step 4).

We realized that this selection process is possibly subjective, since every member of the task group has a personal preference for selecting definitions, formed by education and background. However, such a personal preference can never be avoided, and we simply accepted this fact and trusted on scientific professionalism in the discussions that would follow later in the selection process.

The screenshot shows an Excel spreadsheet titled 'SERENA_Task 2.1 Longlist for selection+SES-2.0.xlsx'. The spreadsheet contains a table with the following columns: Definition term, Definition text, Data source, General comments, and preference columns for IUNG, BAW, INRAE, and WR. The rows are categorized by 'Soil Quality', 'Soil Health', and 'Soil Fertility'. The cells in the preference columns are color-coded: green for preferred, orange for possible, and red for not suitable. The table includes various definitions related to soil quality, soil health, and soil fertility, along with their respective data sources and general comments.

Figure 1 - The Excel sheet with terms and definitions and the preferences of the different partner teams. Columns 1..8: definition term, definition text, definition source, comment and IUNG, BAW, INRAE, WR preferences (green = preferred, orange = possible, red = not suitable). The complete Excel sheet is given in Annex 1.

3.5. Step 4 – the draft list of definitions

After discussing the various options for definitions of the blue list of terms, we finally arrived at the draft list that was then presented to the SERENA project community to comment on. In a presentation on April 28th, during an online project meeting, the list was discussed. The discussion centred around the terms 'soil quality', 'soil health' and 'soil threat'. These definitions are key in the definitions list and in the whole project. After presenting these terms and their definitions, a lively discussion followed. Since it was difficult to find agreement in the SERENA project meeting on these three definitions alone, we decided it was best to let the different partner groups think about the draft definition list a bit longer and let everyone comment on the list in writing instead of during an oral discussion. This is further elaborated upon in step 5 - paragraph 3.6 below. The draft list of definitions as was developed by the task group is presented in Table 2 on the next page.

Table 2 - The draft blue list of definitions after step 4 - selection by the task group. Column one represents the term, column two contains the (adapted) definitions and column three contains the source of the definition. The blue text in column two represents the adaptations made by the task team. The definition of 'soil threat' still contains the word 'agents' that would later disappear.

Term	Definition	Source
Soil Quality	Soil quality is the capacity of a soil to function as a vital living system, within natural or managed ecosystem boundaries and land-use boundaries, to sustain biological productivity and plant, soil organism and animal productivity and health, maintain or enhance water and air quality, and to further provide ecosystem services on the long-term without (increased) trade-offs between ES (after Doran 1996, Karlen et al. 1997, and Giuffr et al. 2021).	Combined SIREN (Faber et al., 2022) / EEA report (Baritz et al., 2022) Definitions
Soil Health	Soil Health is (then) derived from local SQ specifications, and is the actual (current) condition of the soil, as monitored and measured with dedicated indicators (which we traditionally still call Soil Quality Indicators).	Combined SIREN (Faber et al., 2022) / EEA report (Baritz et al., 2022) Definitions
Soil Fertility	Soil fertility is the ability of a soil to sustain plant growth by providing essential plant nutrients in available form, water and favorable chemical, physical, and biological characteristics as a habitat for plant growth.	https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/areas-of-work/soil-fertility/en/
Soil Function	Soil Functions are one or a combination of soil processes that underpin the delivery of ecosystem services. In this definition, soil functions are comparable to the potential provision of ecosystem services.	Combined SIREN (Faber et al., 2022) / EEA report (Baritz et al., 2022) Definitions
Soil Threat	Soil threats can be defined as processes or agents* that could deteriorate (some of) the functions of soils and the services that soils provide.	EJP Soil Glossary
Ecosystem services	The direct and indirect contributions of an ecosystem to human well-being (TEEB, 2010)	Combined SIREN (Faber et al., 2022) / EEA report (Baritz et al., 2022) Definitions
Soil Ecosystem Services	ES are soil related if their supply is directly and quantifiably controlled by soils and their properties, processes and functions.	Paul, C., Kuhn, K., Steinhoff-Knopp, B., Weihuhn, P., Helming, K., 2021. Towards a standardization of soil-related ecosystem service assessments. Eur J Soil Sci 72, 1543–1558. https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13022 .
(Soil Quality) Indicator	Single or multiple parameters that are quantifiable using analytical protocols, or modelled integrated 'scores' based on interaction of such parameters, which are responsive to change in management and external drivers of soil quality.	Combined SIREN / EEA report Definitions
Bundle	A set of 'Ecosystem services' that appear together repeatedly in time and space. In a bundle, ES can be positively (synergy) or negatively (trade-off) related. In a "co-occurring bundle", ES are spatially and/or temporally correlated while in an "interacting bundle", ES are mechanistically linked through a common driver or underpinning process.	(based upon:) Potschin-Young M, Burkhard B, Czc B, Santos-Martn F 2018. Glossary of ecosystem services mapping and assessment terminology. One Ecosystem 3: e27110. https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.3.e27110
Service Providing Unit (SPU)	The chemical, physical and biological entities important in delivering a specific ES in a particular service providing area.	Combined SIREN / EEA report Definitions
Service Providing Area	The spatial units providing ecosystem services and is addressable by planning and management.	Combined SIREN / EEA report Definitions (added a part of the definition of Andersson et al.)
Soil Degradation	A change in soil condition negatively affecting the ecosystem's structure, functioning, resilience and/or ability to provide ecosystem services.	SIREN final report (p23)
Thresholds	Thresholds are perceived as values above or below which a significant shift or rapid negative or positive change takes place (Van Lynden et al., 2004).	EEA report (Baritz et al, in prep.), Van Lynden et al., 2004.
Reference values	The reference [value] is a range for an indicator representing its background range for defined conditions, usually defined within the state boundaries of a country, and referring in general to a context of soil type, climatic zone and elevation, and land use and management.	SIREN final report (p26)
Target values	The target value represents the desired status for a particular indicator or set of indicators given specific ecological conditions, land use and objectives for use, by authorities and other stakeholders.	SIREN final report (p26)

3.6. Step 5 - Input from the SERENA project community

Using the draft list of definitions, we organised a commenting round, where the rest of the SERENA partners were invited to comment on the draft list of definitions. This was done by posting the Excel sheet blue list on the SERENA TEAMS file share and creating columns for all partner institutes. In these columns the partner institutes placed their comments on the definitions that were proposed by the task team. (See Figure 2 for an impression overview of the Excel sheet, the Excel sheet itself is added to this report as Annex 2).

Please note that not all partners provided comment. This is also because some partners were part of the task group for T2.1, and their comment was already incorporated in the selection and adaptation of the draft definitions.

Figure 2 - The Excel sheet with terms and definitions and the comments of the different partner teams from SERENA. The green coloured column contained the comments and conclusions from the task group, upon which the final selection / adaptation of the definitions was based. The complete Excel sheet is given in Annex 2.

3.7. Step 6 - Final selection of definitions

In step 6, the final adaptation of the draft definitions list took place by the task group according to the comment of all SERENA partners. It was obvious, but not surprising, to see that many of the arguments presented by the partners had already been addressed by the task team in the discussion sessions that preceded the selection of the draft list. The task team evaluated all the comments and did its best to come up with the most appropriate definition, taking into account everyone's opinion.

The final list with definitions as developed by the SERENA community can be found in Table 3 on the next page.

Table 3 - Final list of definitions developed by the SERENA community under supervision of the T2.1 Task group.

<p>SOIL QUALITY</p> <p><i>Soil quality is the capacity of a soil to function as a vital living system, within natural or managed ecosystem boundaries and land-use boundaries, to sustain plant and animal productivity and health, maintain or enhance water and air quality, and to further provide ecosystem services on the long-term without (increased) trade-offs between ecosystem services.</i></p> <p>Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022).</p>
<p>SOIL HEALTH</p> <p><i>Soil health is the current ability of a soil to function as a vital living system, within natural or managed ecosystem boundaries and land-use boundaries, to sustain plant and animal productivity and health, maintain or enhance water and air quality and to further provide ecosystem services on the long-term without (increased) trade-offs between ecosystem services.</i></p> <p>Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022)</p>
<p>SOIL FERTILITY</p> <p><i>Soil fertility is the ability of a soil to sustain plant growth by providing essential plant nutrients, water and favorable chemical, physical, and biological properties as a habitat for plant growth.</i></p> <p>Adapted after FAO definition of Soil Fertility (online source: https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/areas-of-work/soil-fertility/en/).</p>
<p>ECOSYSTEM SERVICES</p> <p><i>The direct and indirect contributions of an ecosystem to human well-being.</i></p> <p>Original, after (TEEB, 2010).</p>
<p>SOIL CONDITIONS</p> <p><i>The chemical, physical and biological characteristics of soils with a particular focus on those involved in the delivery of ecosystem services.</i></p> <p>Adapted, after Potschin-Young et al., 2016.</p>
<p>SOIL FUNCTION</p> <p><i>Soil functions are one or a combination of soil processes that underpin the dynamics of the ecosystem structure or composition.</i></p> <p>Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022).</p>

SOIL ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Soil Ecosystem Services is the soil-related subset of ecosystem services, directly and quantifiably controlled or provided by soils and their chemical, physical and biological properties, processes and functions.

Adapted, after Paul et. al., 2021.

SOIL THREAT

Soil threats are processes that could degrade (some of) the functions of soils and the services that soils provide.

Adapted, after EJP Soil Glossary (online source: <https://ejpsoil.eu/knowledge-sharing-platform/ejp-soil-glossary/>).

SOIL DEGRADATION

Any short-, mid-, or long-term change in soil state negatively affecting the ecosystem's structure, functioning, resilience and/or ability to provide ecosystem services.

Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022, p23).

ECOSYSTEM SERVICE / SOIL THREAT BUNDLE

A set of ecosystem services, soil threats, or the combination of the two, that appear together repeatedly in time or space, as related to a specific context.

Adapted, after Potschin-Young et. al., 2018, MAES initiative.

SERVICE PROVIDING AREA

The Service Providing Area is the area involved in providing ecosystem services.

Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022. Added a part of the definition of Andersson et al. 2015)

INDICATOR

A single or a set of variables chosen to represent or infer a specific object of interest. Indicators can be measured using analytical protocols, estimated through modelling or expert-based approaches and they can be quantitative, semi-quantitative or qualitative.

Adapted, after Kandziora et al., 2012

THRESHOLDS

Thresholds are perceived as values above or below which negative or positive change takes place.

Adapted, after van Lynden et al., 2004.

REFERENCE VALUES

The reference value is a range for an indicator representing its background range for defined conditions, and referring in general to a context of soil type, climatic zone and elevation, and land use and management. It is usually defined within the state boundaries of a country.

Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022, p26).

TARGET VALUES

The target value represents the desired value for a particular indicator or set of indicators given specific ecological conditions, land use and objectives for use, by authorities and other stakeholders.

Adapted, after SIREN final report (Faber et. al., 2022, p26).

4. The SERENA Conceptual Framework

4.1. Task 2.1 framework task group members

The composition of the group of people that volunteered to work on the framework was as follows: **the framework task group.**

Name	Role	Institute	Beneficiary (B) / Linked party (L)
Rodrigo Antón	Group member	INRAE, France	B1
Isabelle Cousin	Group member	INRAE, France	B1
Janjo de Haan	Group member	WR, Netherlands	B2
Erik van den Elsen	Task leader	WR, Netherlands	B2
David Montagne	Group member	APT, France	L1

4.2. Development of a Conceptual Framework - introduction

In the project proposal the development of a conceptual framework (CF) was described in the summary as follows:

'The links between all these concepts [the relevant definitions concerning soils] will be proposed by defining a conceptual framework. The latter will be based on both the SIREN framework and other frameworks available in the literature. They will be discussed and evaluated by end-users to be modified if needed.'

The definition of the conceptual framework of the project was addressed with the challenge of interconnecting a set of key concepts from the basis of the definitions proposed and validated in paragraph 3.7: Soil Threats, Soil Quality, Soil Health and Soil Ecosystem Services (SES) (Figure 3), where SES are expressed in this case both as supply and as use of ecosystem services (ES). These key concepts are also the concepts used in the original framework of the SIREN project (Figure 4).

Figure 3 - The key concepts used as a basis for the SERENA conceptual framework.

Figure 4 - The framework that was developed in the SIREN project. The framework integrates ecological (left, green) and socio-economic (right, yellow) systems, providing a comprehensively structured approach for evaluation and decision-making in policy and management regarding soil quality and ecosystem services. The square boxes in the framework are measurable/quantifiable, the rounded boxes are mechanistic forces from policy, management, market chains or natural drivers.

The SERENA work dedicated to the conceptualization of an integrated framework has involved a process of reflection and synthesis based on a review of the frameworks available in the literature and on the first attempt by the EJP-SIREN project to establish a framework linking Soil Quality to Soil Functions and Services, in order to present the concepts as clearly as possible in a visual scheme. (Faber et al., 2022).

4.3. SERENA conceptual framework design alternatives

Using the SIREN framework as a starting point, the task group designed several alternative versions of the framework (See Figure 5 - Figure 9), although some of the alternatives diverge quite a lot from the original version.

Figure 5 - CF alternative 1

Figure 6 - CF alternative 2

Figure 7 - CF alternative 3

Figure 8 - CF alternative 4a

Figure 9 - CF alternative 4b (full version)

We discussed the various alternatives, and merged alternative 1 with alternative 2, thereby creating in total 3 alternatives. These 3 alternatives were presented in the SERENA session during the EJP SOIL SERENA meeting in Palermo, Italy, where the participants were asked to vote for the ‘best’ alternatives: these were alternative 3 and 4. The task group then more or less merged these two candidates into a final draft CF, which is described in the next paragraph.

While discussing these alternatives we concluded that it would be important to incorporate different states of ‘health’ of the (agricultural) ecosystem or ‘soil quality’ into the framework, as can be seen in CF alternatives 2, 3 and 4. This introduces a dynamic factor and shows the consequences for the

other system components when the soil quality shifts from e.g. healthy to unhealthy or vice versa, or what happens when e.g. the pressure of soil threats increases or decreases.

4.4. Selection of the final SERENA conceptual framework

These increasingly complex frameworks, are intended to have different uses depending on the type of communication, the target audience etc. They should be seen as equally operational snapshots in a very fast evolving environment in which definitions of concepts are frequently refined - including the evolution in the definition of Soil Health - but not as fully stabilized propositions. The actual framework which was selected by SERENA partners during the first SERENA technical meeting in Palermo (June 9 to 11) is shown in Figure 10.

Its description is focused on the basic concepts considered in its elaboration, which can be presented under the following headings:

- According to several frameworks, including the SIREN framework (Figure 4), the SERENA framework presents **two boxes**, where the first one refers to the natural system, namely **eco-system**, and the second one refers to the **socio-economic system**. These two boxes are inter-linked through a revised form of the ES cascade model proposed by Haines & Potschin (2010) that connects ecological and biophysical components, structures and processes to elements of human well-being through successive stages similar to a 'production chain' (Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011, Czúcz et al., 2020).
- Within the ecosystem side of the framework, the concept of **Natural Soil Capital** is included, based on the ES evaluation framework proposed by Costanza et al. (1997). Soil Natural Capital can be defined as the stock of soil biotic and abiotic mass, solid, liquid and gas, that contains energy, as fundamental driver for the functioning of soils as a biogeochemical reactor, and organization, considering that the level of structure impacts many properties and aspects of soil behaviour (Robinson et al., 2009). Soil Natural Capital is the main driver of the below-ground processes and functions, which together with the aboveground processes and functions associated to the other components of the ecosystem determines the supply of ES by the whole ecosystem under specific conditions and type of use. Different supply levels can be differentiated. The actual supply refers to the ecosystems' ability to generate services from the current states of external drivers, Soil Natural Capital and ecosystem management when the potential supply of ES can be defined as the maximum capacity of the ecosystem to generate services from improved Soil Natural Capital and ecosystem management.
- In the socio-economic side of the framework are situated the **flow** (or use) of ES, and the **benefits** and **values**, representing the part of the supply that is directly or indirectly used or experienced and their contribution to human well-being.
- **Society**, represented in this case by **farmers, institutions and the population**, are the beneficiaries of these benefits and values. They are also responsible for the socio-economic response, through land (use) and soil management.
- The socio-economic responses can increase the pressure of **threats** on soils (e.g. through incentives to increase the production of cultivated biomass as source of energy, which could lead to an increase in the area of cultivated land or an intensification of agricultural practices) that in turn degrades the Soil Natural Capital and ultimately decreases the (joint) supply of SES.

On the opposite, the socio-economic responses can improve Soil Quality, the Soil Natural Capital (e.g. through agricultural practices increasing soil carbon stocks) and ultimately the supply of SES. It is then possible to improve the level of Soil Quality from low to high (as illustrated by the colour gradient from light to dark green) and conversely the level of soil threat from high to low (as illustrated by the colour gradient from dark to light red). An opposite trend is obviously possible and unfortunately still frequently observed. This **dynamic feedback loop linking Soil Natural Capital, SES supply and use with land use and soil management options** through the consequences of the latter on soil threats and Soil Quality is a key element of the different frameworks developed in SERENA (Figure 5...Figure 9, Figure 10).

- Another key component of this scheme is the incorporation of the concepts of **Soil Quality and Soil Threats at the interface between the ecosystem and the socio-economic systems**. Indeed, the levels of soil threats and of soil quality are not static and intrinsic properties of the soil system but the product of the suitability of soil use and management to the Soil Natural Capital.
- The **Soil Health threshold** is visualized in Figure 10 as a 'slider', a parameter that can change in value, that can be integrated into this general framework in two different ways.
 - The first one considers Soil Health as a **particular level of Soil Quality** defined by the socio-economic system through a set of **thresholds** that are currently being developed, especially by the European Joint Program on Soils (EJP SOIL) or the EU's Soil Health and Food Mission Board. Where the soil quality is below that particular level, soils are considered **unhealthy**; and where the soil quality is above that particular level, soils are considered **healthy**. Such incorporation of the Soil Health concept in the SERENA framework is consistent with the soil health indicator framework currently developed by the European Environment Agency (Baritz, 2022). Its consistency with the SERENA definition of Soil Health, i.e. *"Soil health is the current ability of a soil to function as a vital living system, within natural or managed ecosystem boundaries and land-use boundaries, to sustain plant and animal productivity and health, maintain or enhance water and air quality and to further provide ecosystem services on the long-term without (increased) trade-offs between ecosystem services"*; this still needs to be carefully checked.
 - The second way of integrating Soil Health in the SERENA framework considers Soil Health as the **current level of Soil Quality**. It is therefore a dynamic value that increases or decreases under influence of various processes in the feedback loop linking land use and soil management to Soil Natural Capital. This latter conceptualization of Soil Health is perfectly consistent with its current definition in SERENA, but potentially less consistent with other initiatives that SERENA would like to relate to. However, in any case, Soil Health is considered as a particular value, either defined by the socio-economic system or resulting from the current land use and soil management options, within the range of values that Soil Quality may have depending on the diversity of land uses and management. The final choice of one of these two definitions of Soil Health is still under debate inside SERENA. Nevertheless, it will likely depend not only on some SERENA internal discussions, but also on external dynamics as initiated by the ongoing Soil Health Law announced in the EU soil strategy for 2030 for example.

- **External or natural drivers** are also represented in the framework. In this case they are connected in both directions to the ecosystem and to the socio-economic system. These external drivers also act on the levels of Soil Threats.

Figure 10 - A potential framework for the SERENA project.

4.5. Further development of the SERENA conceptual framework, definitions and finalization.

The framework presented in Figure 10 is not yet fully developed and may still be altered under influence of work packages and tasks, that are dependent on this framework and the underlying concepts and definitions. Work in progress and future SERENA work may necessitate alterations of both to keep consistency throughout the project or to maintain agreement among SERENA colleagues.

Work packages and Tasks that are making use of the work presented in this report are WP2 (T2.2, Selecting threats, SES, indicators), WP3 (T3.1, National multi-scale assessments) and WP1 (T1.2, Aligning concepts). Also other WPs and Tasks that make use of specific soil-related terms, or the conceptual framework may require alterations of these concepts.

By keeping the concepts developed in T2.1 flexible and by not treating them as if they were cast in concrete, we help developing a common understanding between partners. The concepts will prove finalized by the end of the SERENA project, the task team of T2.1 will remain responsible for the

delivery of the final version of this report containing the final definitions and framework by the end of the SERENA project.

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Annex 1 - The Excel sheet with terms and definitions and the preferences of the different task team members.

The complete Excel sheet can be found at : <https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:x:/s/SERENAEJP-SOIL/ERSwiDae8JtFnVRmpdfWtcgBOQDWmggInFYP-XmGxS5ZwQ?e=43Vcni>

(in the final report, the file might be linked from somewhere else)

Annex 2 - The Excel sheet with terms and definitions and the comment of the different SERENA partners.

The complete Excel sheet can be found at : https://creagov.sharepoint.com/:x:/s/SERENAEJP-SOIL/EUTj6XYnvz5Bs9hAxaiti7oBwnOQe8JdXoEr_Ck6ev5ODQ?e=NE3XNz

(in the final report, the file might be linked from somewhere else)

